

Digital language and communication training for EU scientists

Project number 2022-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000086749

Protocol: Structured interview

Prepared by: P2 team (Dacia Dressen-Hammouda, Nedjah Zerrouki), P3 team (Sue Birch-Becaas, Alexandra Reynolds), and Associate Partner Université Grenoble Alpes (Marie-Hélène Fries, Caroline Peynaud)

Note: Structured interviews require the interviewer to ask pre-written questions in the same way and same sequence for each respondent or group of respondents. This is helpful where more than one person is collecting the data to allow for comparison between data sets.

Duration: Around 45 minutes.

Number of interviews: 10 per partner (60 total).

Equipment:

If online, videoconferencing software, camera and onscreen recording tool.

If in-person, voice recording tool (portable voice recorder, or good quality telephone/tablet)

Stage	Step	Questions
Introducing the research	Interviewer introduction	Brief self-presentation (depending).
	Brief presentation of the DILAN project	The goal of our ERASMUS+ project is to provide training to EU scientists to support their ability to digitally communicate their research results and reach more diversified audiences. [Check technical features of audio/video if in-person, or of video-conferencing tool if remote].
	Thank participant	Thanks for participating in our study and agreeing to an interview with me today. The purpose of this meeting is to get some background information about you and have a short exchange about your digital scientific communication practices.
	Permission to record	Would it be okay with you if I record our conversation from here on out using a video-recorder / screen capture software XXX? [depending on your situation] We'll make all information identifying you anonymous so that in the final

		research study a reader would not be able to identify you. [The participant should be given the information sheet and asked to sign the consent form at this point]
Asking for background information	Interviewee experience	Could you quickly tell me how long you've worked as a researcher in your field? Do you consider yourself to be a junior or a senior researcher?
	Publication frequency	Do you publish regularly? How often do you publish?
Determining practices for the sharing of research results	Typical genres used to communicate research	Do you communicate your research results in forms other than scientific research articles?
	Use of newer digital forms for communicating research results	Do you ever communicate about your results using newer digital forms like video abstracts? graphical abstracts? podcasts? videocasts? infographics posters? If not, why is that? <i>Possible prompts, if necessary:</i> → <i>Our past research has shown that most researchers were interested in these new digital forms but don't actually use them. Why do you think this is?</i> → <i>In a survey we carried out on digital communication practices in the EU, we found that research articles and abstracts were cited as most important. Do you agree with this? Why do you think this is?</i>
	Media used to share research results	How do you share your research publications with your peers? E.g., open-access databases, an institutional web page, a research blog, research-sharing platforms (e.g., ResearchGate, Google Scholar)? What, if any, forms of social media do you use to communicate about your research (Facebook, Twitter...)?

	Possible influences of researcher's academic institution	<p>Does your institution have a policy for research dissemination?</p> <p>Does it fund dissemination through newer digital forms like videos, podcasts, etc.? Or does it expect more traditional dissemination practices like institutional web pages, open access databases, research-sharing platforms, etc.?</p>
	Non-specialist and multidisciplinary audiences	<p>Do you communicate your research with a wider audience?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If so, with whom? and where? e.g., platforms like YouTube; research blogs; media (press, radio, tv); social networks; Citizen science projects, etc. • If not, do you think it's important that your research targets a multidisciplinary and/or non-specialist audience? <p><i>Possible prompt:</i></p> <p>→ <i>In our past research, multidisciplinary and non-specialist-oriented publications were considered less important than open access. Is this also the case for you?</i></p>
Identifying learning and training needs (i.e., the challenges that digital communication poses)	Use of IT tools	If you communicate about your research using newer digital forms, do you use any particular software, applications or tools to do so?
	Knowledge about creating newer digital genres	<p>Do you know how to make video abstracts and do you have the right tools to do so? Same question for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • graphical abstracts • research blogs • infographics posters • podcasts • videocasts
	Conditions for creating the newer digital genres	If you were to produce these digital forms, would you need to do it by yourself, or

		does your institution have a service that would help you?
	Languages used to share results with peers	Which languages (English? other?) do you use to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • share your research results with your peers? • carry out your research on a day-to-day basis? How do you feel about using English to communicate your research results?
	Languages used to share results with a wider audience	If you communicate about your research to a general public, which language(s) do you use?
	Conditions for using English for research purposes	Do you currently get help for writing up and presenting your research in English? If so, who helps you? E.g., colleagues in your lab or department, online automatic translators (e.g., DeepL, Google), an English-language service at your university, private translation agencies, etc.?
	Question about perceived needs	Do you think you could benefit from support or training in <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • using English for research purposes? • communicating your research in English with the general public? • adapting your message to make it more appropriate to a wider audience? • creating videos, research blogs, making and recording podcasts?
	Other useful genres, tools or media	Are there other types of media or anything else you would be interested in learning about? If so, which ones?
	Question about training format	The training we develop based on our interviews will be online.

		What format would best fit your needs? Independent training modules on your own time? Same-time group training?
	Thank participant. Turn-off (screen) recorder. Contribution to our research	Well, that concludes things / wraps things up for us today. Thanks very much for agreeing to take part in our study – we really appreciate it as we feel it’s so important to get your insight on digital and multilingual communication practices.
Finishing up	Confidentiality	Just to reassure you about confidentiality, all names will be changed in the study as well as for example the names of institutions where you’ve worked.
	Answer any questions from interviewee	Do you have any questions about what we’re planning to do with your participation in our study?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify researchers willing to participate in training module Identify women researchers willing to have Kampal develop a social media profile of them <p>Identify women researchers for the video testimonials</p>	<p>Would you be interested in or willing to participate in the training program (Spring 2025) we will be developing based on our interviews?</p> <p>Would you be interested in participating in a study which would explore your social media profile?</p> <p>Would you agree to participate in a video testimonial about digital science practices?</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow-up information 	For all: If we need any further information, would it be okay to contact you again via email / LinkedIn?